

Fault Current Limiters

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Abstract

The article addresses challenges in the electric power grid stemming from increased renewable energy installations, electric vehicle adoption, and altered power flows. It introduces Superconducting Fault Current Limiters (SFCLs) as a pivotal solution. SFCLs, leveraging superconductivity, provide a fail-safe approach to ensure grid stability during faults. Prototypes utilising high-temperature superconductors have shown maturity, with some reaching pre-industrial stages and undergoing successful field tests. The article discusses resistive and saturated core SFCL types, emphasising their advantages. Challenges include achieving fault withstand capability, multiple fault endurance, and rapid recovery times. The need for cost reduction and increased availability of high-temperature superconductors is highlighted for widespread SFCL adoption in power grids.

Introduction

Anticipated increases in energy transmission and distribution will be driven by the rise of electric vehicles and industrial electrification. Moreover, the installation of renewable power plants alters power flow and protection schemes, increasing short-circuit power. The combination of these effects is a remarkable challenge for the power grid stability, as the increase in fault current levels causes the capacity of circuit breakers to be exceeded, while reversed power flows produce operating conditions that differ from the ones for which the protections were designed. This introduces unexpected hazards for the grid. In fact, an overcurrent occurs in an electric power grid following a fault, producing thermal and mechanical stresses that can damage or accelerate the ageing of components. Moreover, an overcurrent is always accompanied by a temporary voltage disturbance that affects the customers

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directly affected by the fault and may also propagate across the entire network. Therefore, preserving and securing the power grid is crucial for enabling the energy transition.

Solution

Superconductivity is the key to realising fault current limiting solutions [1], which are non-linear devices able to reliably switch from low to high impedance state during a fault, providing appropriate protection with no counter effects on the network in nominal conditions. A flexible, fail-safe, and effective device to guarantee power grid stability under various operating conditions is the Superconducting Fault Current Limiter (SFCL). An SFCL is a device with a negligible impedance in normal operating conditions that can switch to a high impedance state under a fault event. Such a device is regarded as a critical component for modern power systems as it allows for a compromise between the technical need of a strong electric network (able to meet the growing demand for energy with a high-power quality) and its ability to face the high value of fault current cost-effectively.

The insertion of an SFCL into an electric grid can offer several advantages:

1. High short-circuit power and extremely strong grid without hazard for the components in case of fault;
2. Fast action, able to limit the fault current peak and thus reduce the stress on the grid components;
3. An SFCL can be designed to obtain a symmetric component of fault current below the interruption capability of the installed circuit breakers, thus avoiding their substitution in case of network expansion;
4. Passive, i.e., reliable, transition to high impedance state in case of fault;
5. Spontaneous recovery of the low impedance state after fault clearance.

Status

Different concepts of SFCL have been proposed [2], and they have all reached excellent maturity by being widely demonstrated during the last decades through several laboratory-scale prototypes. Some SFCL prototypes have reached a pre-industrial stage of development and have been successfully submitted to long-term field tests. Figure 1 reports the state of the art of SFCL demonstrators. Both first (BSCCO) and second (YBCO) generation high-temperature superconductors (HTS) have been used. More recently, magnesium diboride (MgB_2) superconductor was also introduced. As highlighted in the figure, the most mature concepts of SFCL are classified as resistive or saturated cores type devices.

In a **resistive type SFCL**, a superconducting coil (non-inductive) is connected in series with the grid, as represented in Figure 2.a). Under normal operating conditions, the grid current is below the SFCL critical current: the SFCL shows negligible resistance and is transparent to the grid. During a fault, the grid current rises above the SFCL critical current: the superconducting coil quenches, meaning its resistance increases abruptly, and that limits the fault current. A device built under the European project ECCOFLOW is shown in Figure 2.b).

A **saturated core type SFCL** uses a DC bias superconducting coil to heavily saturate a ferromagnetic core. This core is connected to the grid via magnetically coupled copper coils. This device is represented

in Figure 3.a), and its topology is shown in Figure 3.b). Under normal operating conditions, the core is saturated; therefore, the inductance of the limiter is relatively small, and the device is nearly transparent to the grid. During a fault, the overcurrent desaturates the core, thus increasing the SFCL inductance, as shown in Figure 4.a). An inductive voltage appears, limiting the current. An example of such a device was manufactured by InnoPower Company [3], and a small-scale prototype developed at the NOVA School of Science and Technology is shown in Figure 4.b).

Figure 1: State of the art of superconducting fault current limiters.

Figure 2: Resistive type SFCL (a) Single-phase circuit, where u_{grid} is the grid voltage, Z_{grid} is its short-circuit impedance, i_L is the line current, and R_p is a parallel resistance required for the protection of the HTS element; (b) 24 kV/1 kA resistive type SFCL at a substation in Mallorca island (Spain).

Figure 3: Saturated core type SFCL (a) Single-phase circuit, where U_{grid} is the grid voltage, Z_{grid} is its short-circuit impedance, i_L is the line current, and I_{DC} is a DC current flowing in the HTS coil that saturates the iron cores; (b) topology of the device, where diametrically opposing coils, wound in reverse directions, are connected in series among them and with a grid phase.

Figure 4: Saturated core type SFCL (a) Non-linear inductive behaviour; and (b) small-scale prototype developed at the NOVA School of Science and Technology.

Challenges

Successful limiting ability has been widely proven for resistive type SFCL [4]. Achieving appropriate fault withstand capability, with no damage or deterioration of performance, and immunity to hot spot phenomena in light overcurrent are the main challenges of resistive type SFCL. However, the possibility of withstanding multiple and long-lasting faults with no degradation remains to be fully demonstrated. This is being addressed by developing highly stabilised HTS tapes that can withstand high electric fields without reaching excessive

overcurrent and by industrialising the production process of these advanced materials. Obtaining a short recovery time, compatible with the protections of the power system, is also paramount and must be reached by developing an innovative SFCL design, which integrates a reliable and industrial mature ultrafast mechanical switch to disconnect the superconducting element during the fault-reducing heat injection. Further R&D must be developed, particularly on the electric insulation system, to develop reliable SFCL technology suitable for transmission voltage levels.

Saturated core type SFCL is already mature for application at very high voltage levels. However, optimising their design to make them more compact with better-limiting ability and negligible impact in normal operation will be required to speed up the penetration of this technology. An advanced power electronics solution will also be required to prevent induced current transients in the DC bias coil during the fault, which could degrade the limiting action at the reclosing of the circuit.

Finally, to promote faster penetration of both SFCLs concepts, cost reduction and increased availability of high-temperature superconductors (HTS) must be reached.

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